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Nurses and Midwives in Italian Regions

They increased by an average of 20.74% in the Italian regions between 2013 and 2021.

ISTAT calculates the number of nurses and midwives in the Italian regions. The variable is defined as the number of nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants. Data is available for the period 2013-2021.

Trend of the number of nurses and midwives in the Italian regions in 2021. The analysis of 2021 data on the number of nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants in various Italian regions shows a detailed map of the availability of these essential healthcare professionals, reflecting regional disparities in access to nursing and midwifery care. Molise stands out with the highest density of nurses and midwives (8.6), which may indicate excellent healthcare availability for the population, while Lombardy (5.7) and Calabria (5.6) show the lowest densities, highlighting potential areas for improvement in the distribution of healthcare resources. Regions such as Liguria (7.7), Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol (7.6), and Umbria (7.7) also show high values, suggesting a good capacity to provide healthcare to the population. This regional variation calls for a reflection on health policies and human resource planning in the healthcare sector. The density of nurses and midwives is a key indicator of healthcare quality, directly influencing the system's ability to respond effectively to patient needs, from prevention to acute and chronic disease care, to emergency management. Regions with lower densities may face greater challenges in ensuring timely and adequate quality care, with potential repercussions on citizens' well-being and healthcare management. Moreover, an unequal distribution of these professional resources can exacerbate disparities in access to care across different areas of the country. To address these disparities, targeted policies aimed at attracting and training nurses and midwives in regions with lower densities might be necessary, along with strategies to optimize the distribution and utilization of existing human resources. The goal should be to ensure uniform and high-quality healthcare coverage throughout the national territory, contributing to raising health standards and reducing regional health inequalities.

Trend of the number of nurses and midwives in the Italian regions between 2013 and 2021. The analysis of data on the number of nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants in Italian regions from 2013 to 2021 reveals significant regional variations in both absolute values and percentage growth. These changes reflect not only demographic dynamics and regional health policies but also the challenges and priorities in the health sector in different areas of the country. The region that showed the highest percentage increase is Campania, with an impressive +57.89%, followed by Puglia and Molise with increases of 40.00% and 32.31%, respectively. These data suggest intensive recruitment and training activities in these regions, likely in response to pre-existing shortages in nursing and midwifery staff. Conversely, Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol recorded the lowest growth, with only a 2.70% increase. This might indicate an already optimal starting situation or perhaps greater difficulty

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in recruiting additional staff in this region. Lombardy, despite being one of the most populous regions with a highly developed healthcare system, showed a relatively moderate increase of 9.62%, suggesting that even regions with good infrastructures can face challenges in maintaining and increasing healthcare staff. Noteworthy is the case of Lazio, which saw a growth of 44.90%, indicating a significant effort to improve access to nursing and midwifery services. This could reflect a response to the growing needs of an increasing population or efforts to improve the quality of regional health services. The variation in the availability of nurses and midwives in Italy highlights the importance of targeted and flexible regional health policies capable of adapting to specific local needs and shortages. The overall increase in nursing and midwifery staff is a positive indicator towards improving access and quality of healthcare, but the significant regional differences underscore the need for continuous attention to disparities and specific challenges of each region.

Trend of the number of nurses and midwives in Italian macro-regions between 2013 and 2021. The analysis of data on the presence of nurses and midwives in Italian macro-regions from 2013 to 2021 highlights significant absolute and percentage variations in the supply of these healthcare professionals across the territory. In the period under review, Italy recorded an average increase of 1.2 units, corresponding to a percentage increase of 22.64%, rising from a national average of 5.3 to 6.5 nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants. Looking at regional variations, the Center and the South stand out for having recorded the most significant increases. In particular, the Center saw an absolute increase of 1.7 units, with a notable percentage increase of 31.48%, rising from 5.4 to 7.1 nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants. Similarly, the South showed a strong increase, with the South registering the highest percentage increase (41.30%), rising from 4.6 to 6.5 nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants. The northern regions, while showing less pronounced increases compared to the Center and the South, still recorded growth. The North-West in particular had an increase of 12.96%, the highest among the northern regions, rising from 5.4 to 6.1 nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants. These data reflect not only a general improvement in access to healthcare services on a regional basis but also a potential reduction in geographical disparities in terms of nursing and midwifery staff. However, the high percentage variation in the South and Center regions, compared to the more moderate increase in the North, suggests that investment and improvement policies in healthcare access have had a particularly significant impact in historically less provided areas, thus contributing to greater equity in the distribution of healthcare resources nationwide.

North-South Divide. The analysis of data on the presence of nurses and midwives in Italian macro-regions between 2013 and 2021 indeed indicates the existence of a North-South divide in terms of these healthcare professionals' supply. In 2013, the northern regions already had a higher supply of nurses and midwives compared to the South. For example, the North-East had a value of 6.3 nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants, higher than the national average of 5.3, while the South and the Islands recorded 4.6 and 4.8, respectively, significantly below the national average. In 2021, all regions saw an increase in the supply of nurses and midwives, but with variations that accentuated pre-existing disparities. While the North registered relatively modest increases (for example, the North-East saw an increase from 6.3 to 6.8), the Center and the South showed more substantial improvements. In particular, the South highlighted the highest percentage increase, rising from 4.6 to 6.5 nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants, an increase of 41.30%. The North-South divide seems to be partially reduced. The data actually show the presence of an hegemony of the Center. Therefore,

both the South and the North should converge towards the Center in terms of the number of nurses and midwives.

Conclusions. The number of nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants has increased in the Italian regions by an amount equal to 20.74% on average between 2013 and 2021. If we consider the Italian macro-regions, we can see that the macro-regions where the value of the observed variable has grown the most between 2013 and 2021 are the South with +41.30%, the Mezzogiorno with +41.30%, and the Center with +31.48%. More contained increases occurred in the northern regions. However, if we consider the absolute value, we can see that the Center is the Italian macro-region with the highest number of nurses and midwives per 1,000 inhabitants with a value of 7.1 units, followed by the North-East with 6.8, and the South and Islands with 6.5. It is possible to implement a set of economic and health policies to increase the number of nurses and midwives. Education and training in the healthcare sector are crucial elements to ensure an adequate and qualified workforce. It is essential to increase the number of available spots in nursing and midwifery schools to meet the growing demand for healthcare professionals. Moreover, scholarships and fee reductions for students in these disciplines should be offered to make education more accessible. To quickly integrate professionals from other sectors, accelerated training programs could be developed. Economic incentives play a significant role in attracting and retaining qualified healthcare staff. Increasing base salaries for nurses and midwives is an important step, along with offering hiring bonuses and annual bonuses for those serving in critical or rural areas. Improving working conditions is crucial to ensure the well-being and productivity of healthcare staff. Reducing the maximum number of working hours per shift can help mitigate fatigue and improve care quality. Additionally, it is important to provide psychological support and stress management resources, as well as invest in technologies that reduce manual workload, allowing staff to focus on more complex and meaningful activities. Promotion and recruitment campaigns are necessary to valorize the profession of nursing and midwifery and attract new talent. Moreover, creating mentorship and internship programs can help students interested in entering the field gain practical experience. Finally, international collaborations can offer opportunities for qualified migration and exchange. Establishing partnerships with countries that have a surplus of nurses and midwives can promote the exchange of knowledge and skills, thereby enriching healthcare staff and improving healthcare on a global level.

Declarations

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Appendix

Variazione Percentuale del Numero di Infermieri ed Ostetriche per 1000 Abitanti (2013-2021) per Regione

